

PROFESSIONAL SOCIALIZATION: BEGINNINGS, ENDINGS, AND ENDINGS THAT ARE BEGINNINGS

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The autumn has arrived, and with it the university moves from a slow-paced and empty space, to a bustling campus full of new students finding their way and colleagues starting again on the yearly travel through the academic year. Much to the horror of my partner- who is a summer and warm weather person- I love the autumn, with the crunchy leaves, mushrooms popping up, and fresh academic starts.

I currently have several projects running that on the surface look quite distant from one another, but the past few weeks have been a bonanza of worlds colliding, with overlaps and potential for collaboration turning up in the most unexpected places. I love the creativity that these unexpected overlaps bring.

The morning had been a morning discussing the role of professional socialization in education at our VetMed school in Utrecht; how does one embark on “the individual’s journey in becoming a member of a particular profession, a unique social group, and learning to be part of the culture of that group with all its privileges, requirements and responsibilities” (from a frequently cited definition of professional socialization by Joy Higgs (1)) as a veterinary student- and how do we have students socialized to a profession while at the same time giving them the education needed to change and modernize professional standards?

I switched gears to go to the European Society for Agricultural and Food Ethics (EurSafe) conference in Ede, rather expecting to leave my education “hat” behind in Utrecht. I found myself in a talk by Christian Dürnberger from the University of Veterinary Medicine in Vienna examined socialization of VetMed students *before* entering vet school: what kind of experience do that have with animals? Have they ever done any work in a veterinary practice before entering vet school? In their study, which is also reported in detail in the extended abstract book (2) – most students unsurprisingly reported early exposure to dogs and/or cats (and assorted other animals), and 75% reported not having worked in a veterinary setting before starting VetMed education.

This is useful to know – and I’d be very curious to see this both in our own students in Utrecht and in a European study – but the discussion afterward was what stayed with me the most. One of the points made: what do we expect from our students before starting veterinary medicine? While having practical experience and “knowing what you are getting into” certainly could be useful, why do we expect this from VetMed students and not from, say, philosophers? Is veterinary practice is so different from what students imagine, that we need to prepare them for the reality to avoid disappointment? What does this mean about veterinary practice- is it so harsh that we need to prepare students before they even start, in order to help them cope? Do we need to start at the beginning- before students arrive- to prepare for the end of studies? I wonder if we don’t need to start from the end, to make practice a bit more accommodating to young veterinarians.

In my own professional socialization, this week I completed an 18-month program for Educational Leadership at Utrecht University together with 14 colleagues; it has been an intensive time with collaborations and friendships formed, and has absolutely been an intensive professional socialization period. What kind of educator do I want to be? Where am I a part of the system of higher education, and where do I want to change the system? Being a student again for a while – including all of the social aspects – has shifted the way I look at my work, my teaching, and my values. I can’t help but think, if this has changed so much for me with my greying hair and a few decades of work experience, how much must this do for our students?

Fortunately the end of the program is not the end but the beginning of our plans; we have spent the last months working on plans for disseminating what we’ve learned, plans for new projects, and plans for study trips. I look forward to where this end and beginning are taking us!

1. Higgs, Joy. “Professional Socialisation,.” *Educating Health Professionals : Becoming a University Teacher*. Practice, Education, Work and Society. Rotterdam: Brill (2013) DOI: [10.1007/978-94-6209-353-9_8](https://doi.org/10.1007/978-94-6209-353-9_8)
2. Dürnberger C, Fliri S, Springer S. “Before studying veterinary medicine. A discussion of biographical aspects of veterinary students,.” Brill (2024) doi: [10.1163/9789004715509_061](https://doi.org/10.1163/9789004715509_061)